

**Work package 5:
Operationalisation and
participation in test sites**

**D5.5: Report on participatory
process in test sites**

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AUTHOR(S)	Neil Alloncle, Margarita Stancheva, Hristo Stanchev, Francisco Barboza, Fien De Raedemaecker, Hanneloor Heynderickx, Kemal Pınarbaşı, Débora Gutierrez, Helena Calado, Camila Pegorelli, Javier Garcia Sanabria, Marcello Magaldi, Roberta Sciascia, Eleonore Cambra, Alina Spinu, Ivana Stojanovic
EDITOR	Fien De Raedemaecker (VLIZ), Débora Gutierrez (UAc)
APPROVED BY	Ivana Stojanovic
PROJECT OFFICER	Victoria Beaz Hidalgo

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<p>ABSTRACT</p>	<p>This report presents the participatory processes implemented across six European pilot sites under the MSP4BIO project, which aims to integrate biodiversity considerations into Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP). Communities of Practice (CoPs) were established at each site to co-develop, test, and validate an integrated Ecological-Socio-Economic (ESE) management framework. CoPs contributed to identifying local management priorities, assessing ecosystem services, evaluating trade-offs among uses, and co-designing decision support tools. The report highlights the diversity of local contexts, engagement methods, and dynamics generated. It emphasizes the need for flexible participation formats, strong alignment with official planning processes, and the delivery of tangible outputs (e.g., maps, interactive tools) to ensure local ownership. Lessons learned show the potential of the ESE framework to support marine biodiversity protection and restoration policies, while fostering sustained stakeholder involvement in planning processes</p>
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Contact information:

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- ◆ General deliverable: Neil Alloncle, neil.alloncle@cerema.fr
- ◆ University of Tartu: Francisco Barboza, francisco.barboza@ut.ee
- ◆ The Azores Graciosa Island test site: Helena Calado, helena.mg.calado@uac.pt
- ◆ Cadiz test site: Javier García Sanabria, javier.sanabria@uca.es
- ◆ Belgian part of the North Sea test site: Hanneloor Heynderickx, hanneloor.heynderickx@vliz.be
- ◆ Western Black Sea test site: Margarita Stancheva, stancheva@ccms.bg & Alina Spinu, aspinu@alpha.rmri.ro
- ◆ Northwest Mediterranean test site: Neil Alloncle, neil.alloncle@cerema.fr & Marcello G. Magaldi, marcello.magaldi@sp.ismar.cnr.it
- ◆ Baltic Sea test site: Kemal Pınarbaşı, kemal.pinarbasi@helcom.fi
- ◆ MSP4BIO project: Ivana Stojanovic, is@sustainable-projects.eu

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List of acronyms

BSR – Baltic Sea Region

CBD – Convention on Biological Diversity

CEA – Cumulative Effect Assessment

CoP – Community of Practice

EGD – European Green Deal

ESE Framework – Ecological – Socio-Economic Framework

NGOs – Non-Governmental Organizations

MPA – Marine Protected Area

MSP – Maritime Spatial Planning

PW4B – PlanWise4Blue Project

SPIA - Spatial Pressure and Impact assessment tool

GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation

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1 Introduction

The MSP4BIO has an overall aim to support the implementation of the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030, the CBD Post 2020 Global Biodiversity Framework, as well as the European Green Deal (EGD), by mainstreaming biodiversity into planning and policy decisions on different governance levels, and by developing an integrated socio-ecological management of the marine ecosystems.

The EU Member States are at varying levels of maturity when it comes to Marine Spatial Planning (MSP), and the extent to which biodiversity considerations have been integrated into MSP also differs across them. MSP processes are taking place at the national, also at sub-and-supranational levels, at different geographical scales, and focused on different socio-economic and environmental challenges. The six MSP4BIO test sites reflect this diversity to ensure wider applicability and transferability of the tested approaches by planners and those dealing with MPA designation and management across Europe and beyond.

To ensure that project developments address actual needs in the selected sites, engaging and cooperating with local stakeholders (planners, administrations, researchers, experts, economic stakeholders...) is crucial. That is why Communities of Practice (CoPs) have been a central piece of the project implementation. Their compositions are tailored according to site specificities and management needs. Their involvement in the project activities had two main aspects:

- **Co-development:** CoPs were asked to contribute to the knowledge gap analysis carried out by the project, to prioritize management topics at test site level, to test the different approaches developed and constituting the MSP4BIO Ecological-Socio-Economic (ESE) management framework. This by providing their knowledge of the site as well as data if available and therefore co-develop site specific results and solutions.
- **Validation:** Specific site solutions were presented to the CoPs to obtain comments and feedback regarding their relevance and usefulness for their needs and in further decision-making.

This close relationship with CoPs ensured that the project development suited actual management needs in each of the 6 test sites and maximize the local appropriation of the proposed solutions.

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2 Test sites

2.1 Test sites contexts

MSP4BIO is building the ESE Framework approach by testing and validating developments in 6 test sites across the European waters. Each of those sites shows specificities in terms of scale, environmental and socio-economic stakes, management challenges, MSP or MPA process steps.

The main characteristics of the six test sites are presented in Figure 1 and Table 1 and have been described in depth in the deliverables 5.1¹, 5.2² and 5.3³.

Figure 1 MSP4BIO Test Sites across five EU sea basins

¹ Withouck et al. (2023) Site specific gaps and opportunities to support knowledge-based MSP (Deliverable – D5.1., under the WP5 of MSP4BIO project (GA n° 101060707)).

² Matczak et al. (2024) Test Sites Methodology Including the Participation Strategy (Deliverable – D5.2., under the WP5 of MSP4BIO project (GA n° 101060707)).

³ Stancheva, M., et al., (2025). Site specific solutions for accelerating biodiversity protection and restoration in MSP (Deliverable – D5.3., under the WP5 of MSP4BIO project (GA n° 101060707)).

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Table 1 Overview of the six test sites included in the study, with a description of their ecological and jurisdictional scales as well as the MSP status. (MEOW = Marine Ecoregions of the World). Adapted from D5.1 by Withouck et al. (2023) and updated.

Test site	MEOW Province - Ecoregion	Ecological Scale	Jurisdictional scale	MSP status	Relevant sectors
Azores Graciosa Island – Portugal test site	Lusitanian – Azores	Coastal, waters surrounding the island (971,582 km ²)	Graciosa internal/territorial waters - Azores internal territorial waters (Azores autonomous region, Portugal)	MSP adopted	Fisheries, tourism
Cadiz test site: Cadiz Bay (Gulf of Cadiz, Spain)	Lusitanian – South European Atlantic Shelf	Coastal, Bay (Cadiz Bay ≈ 150 km ² , Sudatlantica demarcation = 14,978.3 km ²)	Part of Spanish EEZ and internal waters under regional competence	MSP adopted	Fisheries, aquaculture, tourism
Belgian part of the North Sea test site	Northern European Seas – North Sea	Coastal, Sub-sea basin scale (3,447 km ²)	Belgian EEZ	MSP adopted, new MSP under final stage	Fisheries, aquaculture, tourism, renewables, mineral extraction
Western Black Sea test site (from Cape Tuzla to Cape Kaliakra)	Black Sea – Black Sea	Coastal, Sub-sea basin scale (2,750 km ²)	Subnational & cross-border (Bulgarian and Romanian EEZ)	Bulgaria: MSP adopted	Fisheries, tourism
				Romania: MSP adopted	
Northwest Mediterranean test site	Mediterranean Sea - Western Mediterranean	Coastal/offshore/deep-sea, sub-sea basin scale (130,000 km ²)	Subnational & cross-border (French and Italian EEZ in the Western Mediterranean Sea)	France: MSP adopted	Fisheries, aquaculture, tourism, renewables
				Italy: MSP adopted	
Baltic Sea test site: Insights from Estonia, Sweden, Finland, and Latvia	Northern European Seas – Baltic Sea	Coastal/offshore/deep-sea, sea basin scale (377,000 km ²)	Transnational (Estonian, Finnish, Latvian and Swedish EEZ)	Estonia: MSP adopted	Fisheries, aquaculture, tourism, renewables, mineral extraction
				Finland: MSP adopted	
				Latvia: MSP adopted	
				Sweden: MSP adopted	

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2.2 Communities of Practice

The six MSP4BIO specific test sites served as validation pilots to showcase and operationalise the systemic approach and management (integrated ESE framework) by engaging key national and local actors in a co-development approach.

Early in the project, the task dedicated to the identification of site-specific gaps and opportunities to support knowledge-based MSP (D5.1⁴) analyzed the different ways through which stakeholders are involved in the MSP processes in each of the test sites. This allowed to identify relevant stakeholders to be engaged, such as marine planners, planning and environmental authorities, regional authorities, NGOs, academia and researchers, blue economy sectors' representatives, private sector, and existing Working Groups.

Then, Communities of Practice were established under the responsibility of partners in charge of each of the 6 test sites. Stakeholder engagement in CoPs was framed by terms of reference established for each test site following a common structure (example for the North-West Med test site in Annex 1). The predicted 4 or 5 interactions to support the ESE development during the project period were introduced through these terms of reference.

North Sea: The CoP was made up with stakeholder representatives from seven organizations/authorities (government, Scientific advisory body to the government, regional authority, NGO, academia, research, fisheries). The largest groups represented government (seven people from two governmental bodies) and research (seven people from three organizations).

Baltic: The CoP engaged experts from the existing HELCOM-VASAB MSP Working Group, the BSR MSP Data Expert Sub-Group, and the HELCOM Working Group on Biodiversity, Protection, and Restoration.

Graciosa Island: The CoP brought together key stakeholders, including representatives from an environmental NGO, the president of the fishermen's association, two planning authorities (one with a specific focus on MSP and another on MPA), researchers, and the tourism sector. Each of these actors played a distinct role in the integration of MSP and MPAs, with planning authorities holding significant influence over decision-making and policy implementation. The NGO, fisherman's association president, and tourism sector served mainly in advisory capacities, to ensure that stakeholders' concerns were acknowledged and reflected in the planning process including biodiversity.

Cadiz Bay: CoP members and stakeholders of Cadiz Bay were mobilized for the interactions. The 3rd interaction about trade-offs and participatory mapping brought together and extended group of stakeholders: Environmental Ministry (3); Regional administration (3); local administration (1); Surveillance service (2); Scientists (4); Private companies (2) and an NGO (1). This interaction was followed up by students (24) and members of the MSP4BIO team (5).

⁴ Withouck et al. (2023) Site specific gaps and opportunities to support knowledge-based MSP (Deliverable – D5.1., under the WP5 of MSP4BIO project (GA n° 101060707)).

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NW MED: The CoP set for the NWMed test site gathered scientific experts, NGOs, MPA managers as well as competent authorities in terms of marine conservation and planning. These stakeholders are deeply involved in ongoing management processes and are actively working on these questions. Evolution from the first interaction, which brought about 10 CoP members together, to the 5th one which was enlarged to about 30 people.

Black Sea (Bulgaria): Originally 18 stakeholders' representatives were engaged: ministries and administrations (competent authorities) responsible for MSP and for MPAs management, up to environmental NGOs, local fishers' associations and maritime museum. Exchanges were opened to a broader attendance to the 4th CoP interaction (demonstration and validation of the initial draft of ESE management framework).

Black Sea (Romania): The CoP engaged a variety of different stakeholders: Ministry of Environment, Water and Forestry (in charge with the implementation of MSFD and Habitat Directive, having responsibility also on MSP Directive), Maritime transport (representant of Maritime Transportation Authority), fishing and aquaculture (National Agency for Fishery and Aquaculture - the main actor in developing the national strategy and specific regulations in the field of fishing and aquaculture, having the responsibility for defining and implementing the policy related to the conservation and management of living aquatic resources in natural fish habitats), environmental NGO (focused on the conservation of biodiversity and the rational use of resources in general, and specifically on marine mammals in the Black Sea), scientists (representative of the Maritime Hydrographic Office, the national authority in the field of maritime hydrography activities, navigation safety, and the management of the national maritime hydrographic information system).

3 CoP engagement in ESE development, testing and validation

The aim of MSP4BIO implementation in each of the 6 test sites has been two-fold and CoP contribution was crucial to support this work. First, CoPs were asked to provide feedback/material on the test site priorities in terms of marine protection and spatial planning, leading to the elaboration of the so called “guiding questions”. Second, implementation of the ESE framework or a part of it is deemed to address these questions and to provide answers or perspectives toward management solutions to be used in the future.

CoP engagement was structured around 4 to 5 different interactions, as agreed with CoP members at the beginning of the project. The first interaction was the occasion to introduce project objectives and structure to CoP members and confirm test site priorities and needs, to collect information on data availability and remaining data gaps in each test site. Then, the second interaction was dedicated to the definition of the guiding questions, supporting the scoping phase in the ESE methodology which was essential to build MSP4BIO D5.2 “Test Sites methodology including the participatory strategy”⁵. This

⁵ Matczak et al. (2024) *Test Sites Methodology Including the Participation Strategy (Deliverable – D5.2., under the WP5 of MSP4BIO project (GA n° 101060707))*.

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second interaction was also an opportunity to address and prioritize ecosystem services in test sites to support implementation of the dedicated task on the development of socio-economic and governance criteria, building the socio-economic dimension of the ESE Framework. The third interaction was designed to support participatory mapping and trade-off methodology testing of the ESE framework. Finally, the two last interactions were dedicated to the presentation and validation of the ESE Framework and of the site-specific solutions developed so far through application of MSP4BIO ESE Framework tools in each of the test sites.

3.1 Gap analysis and test site priorities

Beyond introducing the project objectives and structure, the first interaction with CoPs aimed at two main objectives. First, it was expected to complement the gap analysis carried out by MSP4BIO partners with the CoP members' knowledge and needs. Additionally, it provided an opportunity to capture the perceptions of CoP members regarding the predefined priorities and main management needs and opportunities in each of the test sites. The methodology for these activities was developed within Task 5.1 and a detailed description of the methodology can be found in D5.1⁶.

These two objectives were addressed through individual interviews (face to face or by phone calls) or workshops. Some questionnaires were also sent by email. Different engagement approaches were applied according to the test site lead assessment of the best way to engage different stakeholders in the test site. A guidance document was developed to provide questions about four topics of interest (see Annex 2):

- The current status of the MPA network
- The coherence between area designations and the (transboundary) MSP process as well as related governance such as MSFD
- The integration of social and economic aspects with MPAs
- The (re)building of stakeholder confidence in the MPA/MSP implementation

For each of those four topics, some questions were mandatory to be addressed at all test sites, while others were optional, to be addressed or not, depending on the site's specificities. This approach supported comparisons among test sites and allowed for addressing specific needs.

These results fed the Deliverable 5.1 "Site specific gaps and opportunities to support knowledge-based MSP⁷ and paved the way to the identification of the management guiding questions elaborated during the scoping phase.

⁶ Withouck et al. (2023) Site specific gaps and opportunities to support knowledge-based MSP (Deliverable – D5.1., under the WP5 of MSP4BIO project (GA n° 101060707)).

⁷ Withouck et al. (2023) Site specific gaps and opportunities to support knowledge-based MSP (Deliverable – D5.1., under the WP5 of MSP4BIO project (GA n° 101060707)).

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3.2 Framing the test sites priorities for ESE Framework development

During the scoping phase, the second interaction asked CoPs to identify relevant management questions (called guiding questions) suggested by test site coordinators according to different level of detail, from general management questions to specific topics to address them. For example, a quite general question such as “how to anticipate climate change in the MPA network?” could be specified as “how to identify and prioritize area to be protected according to climate change projections?”. This could lead to more specific questions such as “how to anticipate the changes in biotopes?” or “how to identify the sheltered areas (refugia)?”. This last level of specificity appears to be adequately addressed by the ESE approach.

Following dedicated guidance (Annex 3), these interactions were organized in plenary sessions, in presence or online, according to local constraints and opportunities. Some sites carried out these through bilateral interviews to collect more accurate information on stakeholder perceptions.

These exchanges with CoPs allowed to point at different guiding/management questions in each of the test sites. This material was reorganized by MSP4BIO partners through the ESE operationalization step by step methodology (D5.2⁸) and links with the implementation of the different ESE components could have been secured.

For example, in the Black Sea test site, a broad question about the anticipation of climate change effects on the MPA network was specified on the identification and prioritization of climate refugia areas and finally to the finding or development of related indicators that could be addressed by ESE1 (Ecological toolkit) and relevant management measures addressed in ESE3 (Trade-off methods and nature inclusive operation in blue economy sectors).

In the Mediterranean cross-border site, the general management question about achieving the CBD objectives by 2030 (30% of protected areas and among them 10% of strict protection) was specifically oriented to the cetacean conservation in coherence with the current management processes (Pelagos sanctuary, ACCOBAMS regional organization...). This raised specific questions about the identification of priority areas that could be addressed by ESE1 and the elaboration of management strategies at transboundary scale.

Guiding questions defined for the ESE Framework application per test site are available in detail in D5.2⁹.

⁸ Matczak et al. (2024) *Test Sites Methodology Including the Participation Strategy (Deliverable – D5.2., under the WP5 of MSP4BIO project (GA n° 101060707))*.

⁹ Matczak et al. (2024) *Test Sites Methodology Including the Participation Strategy (Deliverable – D5.2., under the WP5 of MSP4BIO project (GA n° 101060707))*.

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This scoping phase, carried out in close relation with CoP members, was a crucial step in steering the development of the following ESE modules.

Chosen questions address actual and relevant topics in the test sites. It has been shown by a survey circulated among CoP members during the first year of implementation. Over 16 answers received, more than 80% of the CoP members considered these questions relevant or very relevant.

3.3 Providing information for ESE developments: testing the Ecosystem services and trade-off approaches

CoPs were asked to support the development of several ESE components, particularly those focused on socio-economic aspects. This was done through the 2nd interaction concerning the ecosystem services valuation and socio-economic criteria definition, and through the 3rd interaction for the trade-off methodology.

3.3.1 Ecosystem services valuation

Part of the 2nd interaction was dedicated to the valuation of the importance of the different ecosystem services in each of the test sites and to the identification of relevant criteria to assess and map them. A specific methodology has been drawn up to rank a list of services previously identified in the literature (detailed in D.4.1)¹⁰. Specific guidance was built to support interaction with CoPs (Annex 3).

CoPs were mobilized in different ways according to the local context. Some interactions were carried out online (Baltic, North-West Med), others were conducted in presence due to the lack of use from some stakeholders with computers (Cadiz Bay, Azores) and some test sites chose to send the questionnaire by email and let CoP members filling or prioritizing key questions by themselves (Belgium, Black Sea).

In most cases, valuation was done independently by each of the CoP members to capture the different perceptions without cross-influence.

The approach was quite complex and sometimes difficult for stakeholders to understand. The method was tested in advance on some sites and some materials were simplified. Particularly the criterion description which was quite technical. Specific assistance or guidance were provided to support the exercise.

Another constraint was the size and complexity of several test sites, which had a lot of different situations and services overlapping. To deal with this difficulty, the majority of the test site leaders decided to narrow the area where the assessment was carried out: particular focus to one or several MPAs (Black Sea, Azores, Baltic), avoidance of the coastal area where too many ecosystem services are present (North-West Med).

¹⁰ Pegorelli et al. (2023) *Criteria for the representation of the social and economic dimension of MPAs (Deliverable – D4.1., under the WP7 of MSP4BIO project (GA n° 101060707))*.

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It was also noted that quoting services and criteria is not that simple and could be suggestive. Standardized scaling could serve as a reference to carry out such an exercise.

Finally, it was mentioned that this kind of exercise is time consuming, both for project partners and CoP members. It should be well anticipated to be able to touch a significant sample of stakeholders in each site.

3.3.2 Testing the Trade-off methodology with CoPs

Following the ecosystem services valuation, one of the major objectives of the MSP4BIO socio-economic ESE2 and ESE3 modules was to elaborate and test a methodology that identifies trade-offs between these ecosystem services and supports decision-making when management decisions are needed. Trade-offs occur when pursuing one objective or maximizing the use of a particular ecosystem service comes at the expense of other services or priorities. Trade-offs arise when managing ecosystem services and deciding how to allocate multiple resources. For example, converting a natural coastal ecosystem into a tourism enterprise may lead to habitats and species loss and reduced water filtration capacity, affecting other services such as coastal protection and water quality.

The method proposed, detailed in D4.3, “Trade-off method for protection and restoration in MSP”¹¹, focused on the MPA design process and was based on the elaboration of management scenarios that were compared thanks to a participatory mapping tool.

It was tested in the test sites engaging CoPs through a dedicated interaction (the 3rd one in the sites). The participants taking part in the testing exercise were mostly members of the established CoPs. Some test sites took a broader approach, such as Cadiz, which opened its interaction to other stakeholders interested in the region. This was mainly because Cadiz aimed at basic information gathering and focused on establishing a framework. In the Azores and North Sea, new members were included in the CoP in the discussion. The other test sites primarily had CoP members with a few absences in the meeting. The proposed methodology has the potential to enhance stakeholder interest and engagement, fostering co-development of the ESE.

Most of the trade-offs analyzed were those concerning marine conservation and economic development. Some addressed as well cultural values or the question of simple versus multi-use.

It has been shown that data/knowledge availability is a crucial aspect in the exercise. Some gaps were pointed out during the exchanges, particularly when trying to map ecological or socio-economic values. Conversely, some sites experimented a large amount of data which put also a challenge in terms of dealing with complexity as well as data management in the participatory mapping application.

¹¹ Gutierrez D., Calado H., De Bruyn A., et al., (2024). *Trade-offs method for protection and restoration in MSP – ESE3 (Deliverable – D4.3., under the WP4 of MSP4BIO project (GA n° 101060707))*.

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To be effective, the trade-off exercise should be carried out through legitimate governance. This lack was a major difficulty in Cadiz Bay. Enlarging the scope to MSP rather than strictly focusing on the MPA designation could facilitate reflection, as was experimented with in the North Sea. It should also limit stakeholder fatigue by merging different demanding processes that are deeply interconnected in any case. Considering existing management approaches (regulation at different scales), it appears essential to stick to the ongoing processes and raise stakeholder interest. In some test sites such as Gaciosa island (Azores), this was ensured by coordination and preliminary exchanges with competent MSP authorities.

3.4 Validating ESE and test site solution

After specifying management topics in each test site and testing the socio-economic approach, steps that could be considered as the “co-development” of the ESE framework, the next interactions with CoPs were dedicated to the presentation of the initial draft of project developments and decision support tools elaborated and updated, followed by showcasing and validating of the test-site specific planning solutions developed (encompassing the use of ESE modules and decision support tools). This step was carried out through one or two subsequent interactions (4th and 5th) with CoPs, depending on the test site's specifics and stakeholder availability.

The project development in Baltic Sea test sites aimed at analyzing spatial pressures and impacts within HELCOM Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) using the HELCOM SPIA (Spatial Pressure and Impact assessment) tool. As the approach had been validated in the Baltic during a previous event, its effectiveness was not a question. Main comments coming from the CoP consultation were about the effective management of MPAs.

In the Belgium Part of the North Sea, the objective was to propose marine reserves designation as a prospective exercise. Scenarios produced using the ABC planner tool were compared with the currently revised MSP and showed some overlap between areas at stake for marine conservation and future offshore wind farm development zones.

The Azorean test site aimed to expand an existing MPA in Graciosa Island, focusing on balancing environmental and socio-economic objectives. A trade-off approach with participatory mapping was implemented to achieve it. It is also expected that this exercise will strengthen stakeholder awareness of current management issues and challenges.

The Cadiz Bay test site was more focused on strategy. It aimed at creating a holistic management framework for the bay, addressing governance gaps, enhancing public participation, and fostering collaboration among institutions. The validation interaction with the allowed CoP members to comment on operational proposals such as designing a shared strategy for the Bay of Cadiz or creating a fund linked to the implementation of the strategy. Opinions, potential and barriers were identified and discussed. Moreover, CoP members offered additional suggestions and ideas to address the key issues expressed by the guiding questions.

The North-West Med test site aimed to support the MPA designations, particularly concerning the strict protection, specifically with regard to two environmental compartments: the deep habitats and the cetaceans. Since the test site was shared

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between France and Italy, the cross-border coherence of conservation strategies was a crucial question. The last interaction with CoPs brought together CoP members as well as other relevant experts (scientists and managers) to discuss the strict protection concept applied to the two ecological compartments. Then, based on an interactive web-mapping tool, priority areas were collectively identified.

In the Bulgarian part of the Black Sea looked at supporting the enlargement of an existing MPA and to understand its socio-economic effects. It was also deemed to enhance coordination between MSP and MPA management as well as cross-border coherence with Romania. A trade-off analysis with participatory mapping and cumulative effect assessment approach were carried out to do so. Finally, MPA integration in MSP was foreseen by building scenarios with PlanWise4Blue software. CoP members, particularly administration in charge of MSP and MPA management, expressed their interest in adopting the solution and using the tools developed.

Trade-offs, participatory mapping and Cumulative Effect Assessment were also carried out in the Romanian part of the Black Sea. Expected outcome were similar: optimizing MPA management and fostering integration in MSP. Scenarios for incorporating aquaculture as a future use in the current MSP are site-specific. Developed solutions addressed the need to revise MPA objectives, management plans and monitoring programs. Collaboration between concerned stakeholders and their engagement was also an objective. The application of CEA within the test site was positively perceived by the CoP members. Opportunities for transferability and scaling up of the proposed solution to other sites or at the national level were identified by the project partners leading this test site.

4 Uptakes and local dynamics created

4.1 CoP Engagement throughout the project period

The MSP4BIO project set up CoPs of different sizes (from less than ten to almost 20) depending on the different test sites, their specificities and their proper needs in terms of management.

The nature of CoP members differed from one site to another, but local / national MSP and MPAs management authorities were represented in all cases.

Attendance to the different interactions also varied depending on the expectation for each of those (Table 2). In general, more people were involved in the first interaction about test site specificities and needs and in the last interaction presenting specific solutions developed on each site. A more focused attendance was relevant to addressing topics such as ecosystem services assessment or trade-off analysis. Therefore, CoP subgroups could have been created to deal with these steps.

During the MSP4BIO implementation and CoPs consultation process, it became apparent that stakeholder engagement needed to be expanded beyond CoP members. For

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example, every Baltic country wasn't represented by an expert for each topic addressed. This led to enlarged consultation, by using CoP members' connections with other experts, for instance. In the North-West Med, the validation workshop (5th interaction) was the opportunity to widely discuss environmental management in the area, involving a significant number of experts and managers outside of the CoP. In Cadiz Bay, national stakeholders were invited to attend some interactions to ensure the coherence between local and national scales.

Table 2: Overview of the number of people engaged in each interaction in each test site.

Number of people involved in each interaction	1 st interaction Gap analysis	2 nd interaction Guiding questions and ecosystem services	3 rd interaction Trade-off	4 th interaction Presentation of project development and tools	5 th interaction Presentation and validation of test site solutions
Baltic Sea	7	20	20	20	20
North Sea	13	5	7	3	-
Azores	5	3	6	3 (4 th and 5 th interactions merged)	
NW-Med	19	5	4	8	42
Cadiz Bay	14	9	40	10 (4 th and 5 th interactions merged)	
Black Sea (BG)	8	6 CoP members for questions 3 experts for ecosystem services	6	20 (BG and RO)	6
Black Sea (RO)	9				

4.2 Uptakes and future perspectives

Beyond the proper ESE framework testing, test sites solutions developed throughout the MSP4BIO project are mostly deemed to support ongoing planning or conservation policies.

In the Baltic Sea, the assessment of impact levels on HELCOM MPAs, done at the regional scale, could be integrated into the green infrastructure map, which is an objective of the Baltic MSP roadmap. Capacity building actions could be foreseen.

In the Belgian part of the North Sea, the project proposals couldn't be incorporated to the new MSP anymore due to the advanced stage of the process. It has been noted that this exercise carried out thanks to MSP4BIO could set the basis of a shift from a participatory process to a co-building one, in the long term.

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In the Azores, the proposed solution for the Graciosa test site can be effectively integrated into the current stage of the MSP process, thus enhancing the designation and management of MPAs. Results had been transferred to the group responsible for developing the MPA revision in the Azores. This integration considers biodiversity attributes and ecological connectivity, ensuring that local conditions and specific marine ecosystems were adequately considered in the planning efforts.

In Cadiz Bay, perspectives to enhance the MPA management were indented such as local cooperation between municipalities as well as cooperation with regional MSP agencies. Reaffirming local governance was evocated. The development of a shared agenda and the creation of a dedicated fund could constitute solutions to overcome policy barriers such as fragmented governance and lack of collaborative political culture. Further implementation of these perspectives still needs to be clarified.

In the North-West Mediterranean, the strictly protected area designation process is still ongoing in the French waters. Assessments and proposals from MSP4BIO will be shared with the relevant authorities to support further designation. Moreover, the web-mapping application set up thanks to the project, will be maintained and enriched along the designation period.

In Bulgaria, an update and revision of the MSP Plan is envisaged to be conducted until next year 2026. The planners find the MSP4BIO solution and the results feasible and important for integration into the revision of the Plan. Moreover, integrating the solution into the MSP process would enhance institutional and cross-sectoral collaboration, as well as capacity building on trade-offs and cumulative impacts for MSP and MPA stakeholders, which would be beneficial for implementing the solution effectively. Applying the trade-offs and CEA would be undertaken in the practical use of this revision of the MSP Plan. MSP and MPAs competent authorities are members of the Bulgarian CoP and have been actively involved during the project, ensuring appropriation of the results. Additionally, the Black Sea Commission and the Black Sea Economic Cooperation Organization were involved.

In Romania, the results of the PlanWise4Blue (PW4B) CEA tool should be included in the process of designation of new MPAs or the establishment of a strictly protected areas. Scale up the use of CEA and ecosystem-based planning into national MSP process and economic development strategies.

5 Stakeholder engagement: Lessons learned and main challenges

Lessons learned on carrying out consistent participatory processes come from several project actions.

Feedback from the different engagement processes in each of the test sites over the whole project allows us to point at good practices and challenges.

Several final validation workshops were also organized in Cadiz and Romania, and a during the MSP4BIO final event held in Venice on 3 July 2025 where CoP members from

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Black Sea and Baltic Sea were attending. These exchanges confirmed the importance of MSP4BIO results and their future use in MPA/MSP processes and were also a good source of feedback concerning the participatory approaches.

Moreover, two questionnaires were developed and distributed among the stakeholders in MSP4BIO CoPs, one in the middle of the project and the other one at just before the project completion, to obtain their feedback on the Communities of Practice format and interactions and MSP4BIO implementation. Results are summarized in the brochure presented in annex 7.

In addition, over the course of the project, six cross-site interactions have been organized by the project coordinator among test site leads, discussing their challenges in the work with CoPs, but also good practices and lessons learnt.

5.1 Key insights from CoP members and test site leads throughout the project implementation

Engagement of CoP members has been influenced by several barriers, including limited time, technical language, in some cases lack of topic familiarity (e.g., ecosystem services, policy), limited digital skills, and sometimes unclear relevance to national processes. To improve engagement, stakeholders have expressed a need for more accessible, concrete outputs—such as interactive tools, visual maps, and simplified presentations of results. Upcoming demonstrations of the ESE and its tools and fewer but more focused workshops were highlighted as effective strategies, as seen in successful cases like Cádiz, Black Sea and the Azores.

Based on that input, further CoP activities were carefully planned with simpler, less technical language and coordinated closely with tool developers to ensure alignment with ongoing national and regional processes.

CoP interactions have been valuable in identifying knowledge gaps, supporting participatory mapping, and proposing new MPA areas contributing to the CBD 30x30 goals. However, for broader uptake, less project-based, and more inclusive and adaptive engagement formats are needed, especially involving local stakeholders.

Key recommendations that have been taken on board in the final interactions on tool testing and solutions validation:

- Organize focused, where possible, in-person ESE tool testing sessions tailored to national contexts.
- Involve additional local stakeholders to improve sectoral representation.
- Prepare stakeholder interactions as early as possible, avoiding overly technical content.
- Better adapt engagement formats to site-specific realities.
- Evaluate the CoP format's long-term potential beyond the project, as stakeholders find more value in continuous engagement.

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Results from all these interactions showed that positive feedback from test sites confirms the potential for MSP4BIO tools to influence upcoming national MSP and MPA revisions (e.g., Azores, Black Sea, Belgium, Poland, and Spain). However, the long-term effectiveness of CoPs is best realized when integrated into broader, enduring policy and planning frameworks.

6.2 Lessons learnt

Throughout MSP4BIO implementation, different interactions with CoPs showed interest from stakeholders on specific projects activities and outcomes. Several lessons could be taken in terms of consultation format to maximize their effectiveness and stakeholder interest.

The scoping phase was an important step in the project that allowed us to align CoP expectations with project development possibilities. It ultimately resulted in concrete applications to be tested, ranging from ecological expertise, thanks to ESE1 development, to socio-economic assessments through ESE2, or the production of scenarios in ESE3. About 80% of the CoP members who answered the questionnaire on the ESE implementation were satisfied with this scoping phase.

Trade-off exercises also raised an important interest from CoP members. It was an opportunity to address actual questions based on test site maps and discuss them among different groups of stakeholders, bringing together various sectors and aiming toward participatory mapping. The concreteness of exchanges appears as a crucial point in stakeholder consultation.

Decision Support Tools are also very appreciated. Optimization tools such as ABC planners or cumulative effect assessment tools such as the one run in PlanWise4Blue or Tools4MSP provided an innovative point of view and assessment on the topics of interest in each test site. CoP members showed a real interest in testing and validation of different tools available. However, attention must be paid in the adequacy of the elements provided by the tools and questions pointed out. The availability of data, knowledge, and resources also needs to be carefully considered to ensure the effective implementation of such tools.

In terms of CoP interaction format, various approaches were explored on the size of the stakeholder group consulted or on the in person or remote way. One of the main conclusions is that consultation strategies have to be specific to the site context (complexity of the management questions, ongoing management processes and associated governance experts' availability...).

This flexibility could also be considered between the different steps of the project solutions' development. Some steps require specific expertise and could be more efficiently worked on in smaller, specific groups, while other steps need stakeholders and decision-makers' perceptions and are relevant to be addressed in larger groups. Some test sites experimented with this consultation size variations and concluded its relevancy. Additionally, it has been noted that the formal aspect of the engagement in CoPs for stakeholders (through the signature of a consent form for example) is a limitation to the engagement dynamic. These limitations have been addressed by the MSP4BIO project through providing registration tools (online or paper ones), reflecting GDPR rules and

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outlining the scope of engagement and participants' rights, therefore reflecting the main content of the Informed consent forms.

It has been noted that CoP members could be more or less active in the process depending on their availability and their level of expertise on questions addressed. Various projects are often running in parallel and are looking for field inputs. This could cause stakeholder fatigue leading to lower engagement. Synergies between projects should be looked for and could create a long-lasting engagement process. Additionally, the number of interactions should be rationalized: comprehensive workshops appeared more efficient than successive short consultations. In person workshops, when feasible, bring more effective results than online meetings or email consultations.

When interactions are planned at a transboundary scale, attention must be paid to mutual understanding of the different national management processes and national policies expectations. Sharing the same vocabulary is also crucial to avoiding misunderstanding. Finally, the link to official processes is crucial. Project outcomes with regard to ongoing management should be made obvious for stakeholders asked to contribute. A good understanding of this added value is a strong ingredient in engagement dynamics. This objective could be achieved by building close cooperation with competent authorities, engaging or at least communicating results to relevant governances and by delivering concrete results such as maps or tools.

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6 Conclusions

Support from Communities of Practice was crucial in the project implementation. This to ensure that developments (assessments, solutions, tools...) addressed correctly current management needs in test sites, could be properly appropriated by stakeholders and decision makers and could be transferred to other sites.

Building confidence and dynamic in consultation throughout the project is a major challenge. Concreteness of the expected results and alignment with ongoing management processes (MSP, MPA designation or management...) are crucial to raise stakeholder interest.

Most of the solutions developed are expected to be used in site management which shows the efficiency of the stakeholder engagement through CoPs in MSP4BIO.

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7 References

Gutierrez D., Calado H., De Bruyn A., et al., (2024). Trade-offs method for protection and restoration in MSP – ESE3 (Deliverable – D4.3., under the WP4 of MSP4BIO project (GA n° 101060707)).

Matczak et al. (2024) *Test Sites Methodology Including the Participation Strategy (Deliverable – D5.2., under the WP5 of MSP4BIO project (GA n° 101060707))*

Pegorelli et al. (2023) Criteria for the representation of the social and economic dimension of MPAs (Deliverable – D4.1., under the WP7 of MSP4BIO project (GA n° 101060707)).

Stancheva, M., et al., (2025). Site specific solutions for accelerating biodiversity protection and restoration in MSP (Deliverable – D5.3., under the WP5 of MSP4BIO project (GA n° 101060707)).

Withouck I., Rombouts I., De Raedemaecker F., Gutierrez D., Calado H., Costa A.C., Pegorelli C., Garcia Sanábria J., Garcia Onetti J., de Andres M., Stancheva M., Stanchev, H., Spinu A., Boudy C., Alloncle N., Magaldi M., Sciascia R., Barbanti A., Randone M., Pınarbaşı K., Blažauskas N., Kotta J., Lukic I., Stojanovic I. (2023) Site specific gaps and opportunities to support knowledge-based MSP (Deliverable – D5.1., under the WP5 of MSP4BIO project (GA n° 101060707)).

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8 Annexes

Annex 1: CoP terms of reference – Example on the North West Med test site

MSP4BIO: IMPROVED SCIENCE-BASED MARITIME SPATIAL PLANNING TO SAFEGUARD AND RESTORE BIODIVERSITY IN A COHERENT EUROPEAN MPA NETWORK

COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE TERMS OF REFERENCE

The main objective of MSP4BIO is to develop an **integrated and modular Ecological-Socio-Economic (ESE) management framework for the protection and restoration of marine ecosystems**.

Six test sites in five European Sea Basins have been selected to conduct the analysis and to showcase and operationalize the ESE management framework. The test sites reflect the processes that are taking place at the national, sub-and-supranational levels, at different geographical scales, and focus on different socio-economic and environmental challenges.

In order to align MSP4BIO developments with local contexts and needs, **Communities of Practice (CoPs)** are set in each of the test sites. CoPs are meant to foster proper implementation of methodologies developed by MSP4BIO. They are made up of MSP and MPA practitioners and in general way, of stakeholders involved in maritime uses management. Exchanges with CoPs will be made of workshops and focus group meetings. CoPs members could also be asked to inform project partners about relevant information or data that could be used in the management framework setting-up.

NORTH-WEST MEDITERRANEAN TEST SITE

The NW-MED testing site covers a **cross-border area shared between three countries, France, Monaco and Italy** extending from the Gulf of Lion to the Pelagos Sanctuary. The site encompasses different spatial scales: from the local scale characterizing small MPAs to the transnational and cross-border level of the Sanctuary and governance complexity. MSP processes are ongoing at different steps: France adopted its strategic and spatial plan in 2019 and its related action plan and monitoring program in early 2022. The reviewing of the strategic and spatial plan has been launched. Italy is currently (end 2022) consulting for its MSP plan.

Thus, there is a need to **support management alignment** from different point of view: (1) Between MSP and environmental management (MPAs and the environmental policies), (2) across multiple scales from local large areas and (3) at a transboundary level between the 3 countries of the test site.

Ecosystems across the test site are very diverse, from coastal shallow sensitive habitat to large pelagic open sea areas. Loss of key habitats and species must get interest. Among them, coastal

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structuring habitat such as Posidonia bed, sensitive habitats such as gorgonian fields or mobile species such as cetaceans are particularly important and are targeted by management measures.

Diverse maritime uses are also occurring in the area and need for proper attention with regards to their environmental effects. Maritime traffic is a typical transboundary topic to look at, important to consider with regards to the interactions with cetacean and ongoing management processes (Pelagos management, PSSA proposal...). Aquaculture development as well as coastal tourism and leisure activities management are shared concerns between the 3 countries. Renewable planning, with respect to the ecosystems, is a crucial topic for France.

WHAT IS EXPECTED FROM MSP4BIO IN THE NORTH-WEST MEDITERRANEAN?

Analysis, methods and frameworks that will be developed by MSP4BIO aims to support:

- The identification of conservation priorities to progress toward the objectives of 30% of protected areas and 10% of strict protection set by the EU biodiversity strategy.
- The shape or implementation of MSP to foster its effective contribution to the progression toward conservation targets at sea basin level, the MPAs objectives achievement, the MPA network enlargement or any other management measure designation.
- Crossborder exchanges on both MSP and MPA management
- Acceleration of Pelagos sanctuary management

COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE ENGAGEMENT SCHEDULE

1. Scoping

Purpose: Understanding the local state of play and needs & expectations that can be addressed by the project: How can MSP4BIO contribute to the ongoing MPA and MSP processes? What data is available locally and what are the gaps in data and knowledge?

Method: Individual informatory interviews to introduce the project and discuss its relevance to the test site.

Expected output: A summary of needs, expectations and data and knowledge gaps

Time: by 30 November 2022

2. Co-development

Purpose: Guiding and shaping tools and methods to be developed/used. Sharing knowledge about the test site stakes, issues and management processes.

Method: Workshop/group work/focus group meetings

Time: April – May 2023 (tentative)

Expected output: Recommendations and guidelines for MSP4BIO technical developments on ecological, social and economic aspects.

3. Demonstration and validation

Purpose: Testing actual implementation of tools and methods developed by the project. Providing feedbacks to fine tune approaches. Sharing knowledge.

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Method: Workshop/group work/focus group meeting - Participatory mapping, scoring...

Time: March – April 2024 (tentative)

Expected output: Proper implementation of MSP4BIO management framework, adapted to the context of the test site.

4. Adoption and uptake

Purpose: use of the project results beyond the projects lifetime

Method: Sharing and approving final documents. Discussing on the use and uptake of the results, and commitments.

Time: May – June 2025 (tentative)

Expected output: Useful and disseminated outputs. Maximised outcomes.

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Annex 2: Guidelines for the 1st interaction with CoPs

Aim of guidelines:

To clarify what is expected of test site leads for the gap analysis (T5.1), and for the first planned engagement with the CoP (T5.3) aimed to be a scoping exercise, by elaborating on the info on CoP engagement already available on the [Sharepoint](#).

After the desktop analysis part of T5.1 (Phase One), these guidelines provide information on Phase Two (validation of results with CoP members) and Phase Three (integration of desktop analysis results with results from CoP interactions)

Timing

Deadline for conducting interviews (Phase Two): 20th of January

Deadline for the Phase Three integrated report (combined findings of interviews and desktop analysis): early February

Phase Two: Scoping round Community of Practice in MSP4BIO

Purpose

Understanding the local state of play and needs & expectations that can be addressed by the project. Engagement with the CoP members to introduce the project and discuss its relevance to the test site. How can MSP4BIO contribute to the ongoing MPA and MSP processes.

- To clarify current state of play
- Validate and complete our initial desktop study (phase one)
- Aim: to collect missing local information and potentially some specific datasets

Method

The preferred approach is for test site leads to conduct **qualitative semi-structured interviews** with the Community of Practice members. Semi-structured interviews are guided by questions but also allow unexpected insights to be included in the qualitative data collection. The list of questions is used as an **interview guide**¹².

The format of these interviews should be flexible to adapt as much as possible to local contexts regarding potential ongoing consultations with stakeholders and also to consider their availability. They could be carried out either through individual interviews, written questionnaires, participatory meetings, a mix of them or any other appropriate method.

No matter the method, the essential point is to end up with a shared vision of test sites priority topics and collect relevant information on them (see the purpose part above, and Annex 2).

Interview guide

¹² Bernard, H. Russell. *Research methods in anthropology: Qualitative and quantitative approaches*. Rowman & Littlefield, 2006, Chapter 9 p. 212.

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The questions in Part C of the Phase One Guidelines were used to form the interview guide in **Annex 1 of this document**, and is organized into four themes. Core questions are identified per theme to prioritise the data collection.

Four themes of the study:

1. Status of the current network of MPAs
2. The coherence between MPAs/OECMs and the (transboundary) MSP process as well as related governance such as MSFD
3. The integration of social and economic aspects with MPAs
4. The (re)building of stakeholder confidence in the MPA/MSP implementation

The **core questions** for each of the 4 themes (see Annex 1) need to be addressed in every test site to ensure a minimum of homogeneity and enable a cross comparison at the project scale. Answers to these core questions should enable prioritisation of issues, needs or data/knowledge gaps for each of the 4 themes and could **drive the selection of additional questions**.

Then, depending on the test site context and the profile of the CoP member, several **additional questions** (see Annex 1) could be addressed. The additional questions can be seen as sub-questions to the core questions or side topics. **Questions in bold with an asterisk (*)** indicate questions that are useful for other WPs, so these can be prioritised, and can also be revisited in the second round of interactions with the CoP members. This also holds true for the reserve list questions which will feed into other WPs. Please find a table below with an explanation of the different question types.

Question type	Explanation
Core questions	Each question should be asked to at least one CoP member per test site
Additional questions from other WPs	These questions, marked in bold and with an *, will feed into the work of other WPs and should be prioritised as additional questions, and can asked to CoP members with relevant expertise
Additional questions	These questions are optional, and answers to these questions might also result from asking the core questions
Reserve list questions	Questions from WP4 that can also be asked to CoP members with relevant expertise now or if not possible, at a later stage

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The interview questions may need to be rephrased and not all additional questions might be relevant for all CoP members. We expect that based on the desktop analysis or on CoP member feedbacks, test leads will be able to gauge which questions should be prioritised. Each test lead may also include any new additional questions focusing on identified user needs and local issues to get more information and complement the gap analysis. The relevance of each question for the test site will depend on the scale of the test site and on the specific issues and needs identified in the desktop analysis. It is therefore understandable the range of questions asked will be different for each test site.

The interview guide questions are similar to the Section C Evaluation Questions already answered by the test site leads in the desktop analysis. The idea is to capture the perspectives on the CoP members on these questions as well, to enable a comprehensive picture to be formed of the current state of the art, encompassing multiple perspectives.

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Practical interview tips

- Preparation
 - It can be useful to practice the questions on someone beforehand
 - Send the questions to the participants before the interview so they have the opportunity to prepare answers
 - If you have permission from the participants, it can be handy to record the interview in case you missed points you want to revisit
 - For some participants it might be necessary to first introduce the MSP4BIO project and the test site before starting with the questions
 - If an **event with multiple CoP members** will be organised, be sure to keep record of a participant list, as included in the [Event Preparation Toolkit](#) of WP7
- Tips on asking the questions during the interview
 - **Language:** Different language may need to be used depending on who you are talking to (e.g. a policymaker or a recreational fisher will use different terminologies for the same topics)
 - **Translation:** Deepl.com is a useful website for translating
 - **Probes:** It can help to ask questions you already know to make sure you and the CoP member have a mutual understanding of the topics (e.g. repeat an answer by the CoP member as a question to make sure you understood, also called “The Echo Probe” in interview techniques, see [link](#) for more info and more types of probes)
 - **Sequence:** In the ordering of the questions, we tried to keep a sequence going from broad questions to more specific questions, as this can ease the flow of the communication
 - **Validation:** To validate the desktop findings, it could be interesting to guide the conversation based on outputs you already identified in parts A, B and C in Phase One, e.g. “we saw that the conservation objectives for this MPA have been recently updated, do you think this will contribute to meeting the targets of the Biodiversity Strategy”
 - this can help you collect useful specific information
- Wrapping up the interview
 - It could be handy to ask the participants if they are okay with you getting in touch with them for any follow-up questions
 - Let the participants know you will keep them informed on progress of the project and further engagement opportunities (more information on upcoming CoP interactions [here](#))
- Recording results
 - When collecting answers for the questions, make sure you keep originals of filled in questionnaires by the CoP members

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Phase Three: Expected output and format of integrated report

A template for reporting the output is proposed in **Annex 2**

It is expected, per theme:

- **A summary text prioritising needs, expectations and data/knowledge gaps in the considered test site.**
- **Answers to the core questions**
- **If relevant, answer(s) to several selected additional questions.**

NB: Additional themes can be added if relevant information comes out of the interviews outside of the scope of the defined themes/questions.

The Phase Three summary and answers to questions (core and additional) should be the **integration of results from the desktop study (Phase One) and results captured with the interviews with the CoP members (Phase Two).**

Examples on how to integrate desktop analysis and interviews output.

The two following examples should only be taken as illustration of approaches to carry out the interviews and complete the gap analysis report. It is up to each test site leader to shape its own interview approach depending on local contexts.

1/ This first example shows how an open discussion (with one or several CoP members depending on the chosen format) from a core question could provide answers to core questions but also to additional ones. The additional sub-topics popping up could be considered as priorities (to be checked by the interviewer) and specified through additional questions.

Question introducing theme 1: Do you think that current protection offered by the MPA network is appropriate (core question 1.1)? Are there some gaps (core question 1.2)?

Answer from the interviewee: I think that the MPA network covers quite a lot of environmental features at stake on the coasts (feeds into core question 1.2). However, there is no clear protection rule established in lot of them. For instance, nothing changes within the N2000 xxx site. There is a clear gap in MPA management and regulation standards, excepted for Nature Reserves and the hearth of national parks (feeds into detailed question 1.13). On the other side, mobile species are poorly addressed in offshore waters. The point is that there isn't almost any MPA beyond the continental shelf and the one existing such as Pelagos is poorly managed (feeds into core question 1.2 and detailed question 1.13). And we know that there is important migration routes for both marine birds and marine mammals in the study area (feeds into detailed question 1.11 and also detailed questions for theme 2: 2.12 and 2.13).

Extra-question from the interviewer: You pointed out the lack of coverage of the MPA network in offshore areas. Is it due to lack of scientific knowledge (detailed question 1.6) or other reason?

Answer from the interviewee: The point is that we don't have enough long-term monitoring to really figure out what are the important areas for birds and mammals. Moreover, these areas are not stable over years (feeds into detailed question 1.6). It is the same for migratory routes (feeds into detailed questions 2.12 and 2.13). The extent of potential important areas offshore could be addressed by regulations, provided by MSP, rather than MPA designation (feeds into detailed question 2.5 and 2.12).

Extra question from the interviewer: You mentioned the shortcomings in MPA management or regulation. Can you specify these shortcomings (detailed questions 1.12 and 1.14)? Are they due to a lack of knowledge (detailed question 1.6)? Or to a lack of political will?

Answer from the interviewee: ...

2/ This second example show how different answers to the same detailed questions, from several CoP members and from the desktop analysis, can be compiled to complete the gap analysis report.

Question 2.12: Does the MSP provide for protected ecological corridors ensuring connectivity between conservation areas?

Question 2.13: Are migratory routes for birds protected by the provisions of the MSP?

Desktop analysis results:

- No ecological corridors provided at this moment
- Migration corridor maps specifically for seabirds are a research priority to help meet the conservation objective to avoid a reduction in the area available for seabird use within the Belgian part of the North Sea (so work is undergoing)

Results interview CoP member #1:

“Yes, research on these maps are underway”

Results interview CoP member #2:

“We understand the value of such research but what about other potential receptors of impact such as pelagic fish?”

Results interview CoP member #3:

“The targets of the EU Biodiversity Strategy are ambitious and urgent so we need immediate action as well as research initiatives”

Connectivity, ecological corridors and migratory routes (2.12,2.13)

For the Belgian case, to meet the conservation objective of avoiding a reduction in the area available for seabirds to use, research is underway that should identify migration corridors used by seabirds. However, CoP members have iterated that this does not progress conservation of other ecological features of interest such as pelagic fish, and as well as research, other actions need to be put in place to meet the urgent and ambitious EU Biodiversity Strategy targets.

How the outputs will be used

As well as reporting on these outputs in the D5.1 Deliverable, gaps identified during this study will inform how the project can be relevant for each of the test sites. This will be useful for the tasks from other work packages so they can fine-tune their approach according to specific test site needs identified during this gap analysis. For example, answers to Q1.3 will inform T3.1 to understand how current ecological/environmental criteria can be improved.

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Annex 1: Interview Guide

Theme 1: The expansion and strengthening of the current network of MPAs, based on the features of interest in the study areas, with a focus on climate change resilience and connectivity (and setting up management processes)

Theme 1 Core Questions:

- 1.1. Do you think that the current protection provided by the MPA network is appropriate?
- 1.2. Are there gaps in network coverage or in network management?
- 1.3. What do you think about how protected areas are currently designated – do you think the criteria and underpinning data used to inform designations is appropriate?

Theme 1 Additional Questions:

Prioritisation criteria MPA design

- 1.4. What are useful criteria (e.g. biological diversity, fragile and sensitive habitats, etc.) / tools (e.g. cumulative impact assessment, scenario building for conservation prioritization, etc.) you recommend to be used for identification of new MPAs/OECMs?*
- 1.5. Were there any social and economic criteria used for identification of existing MPAs? And prioritisation of areas for protection?*
- 1.6. Is the location of protected areas founded on a clear and transparent scientific rationale?
- 1.7. Are there specific social and economic features to be considered for the designation of new areas?*

Current MPA network and measures

- 1.8. Does the actual network of MPAs in place incorporate principles of ecological connectivity?*
- 1.9. Do the measures in place in MPAs address climate change impacts on ecological features?*
- 1.10. Do the measures in place incorporate social and economic dimensions? (if yes, how)*
- 1.11. Are there features of interest (species, habitats, abiotic features) currently lacking protection?
- 1.12. Which are the gaps in the current conservation objectives?
- 1.13. Are the management plans in place successful for achieving the conservation objectives?
- 1.14. Which are the gaps in the current management practices?

Theme 1 Reserve questions

- 1.15. What is the process to establish a MPA?*
- 1.16. Do the MPAs already established have monitoring and assessment programs going on?*
- 1.17. How mature is the MPA process and how does that affect MPA effectiveness?*

Theme 2: The coherence between MPAs/OECMs and the (transboundary) MSP process as well as related governance such as MSFD

Theme 2 Core Questions:

- 2.1. Do you think that MPA and MSP policies are well connected?
- 2.2. Does the MSP process support the progression toward MPA conservation objectives (within or outside of the MPAs)?
- 2.3. Do you consider that articulation with other environmental policies, such as MSFD or WFD implementation, is effective and clear enough?
- 2.4. Do you think that MSP provides sufficient guidance to maritime uses to prevent environmental impacts?

Theme 2 Additional Questions:

Consideration of MPAs in MSP

- 2.5. **How are the MSP and MPA/OECM/EBSA processes linked?**
- 2.6. **How do MSP(s) relevant to the test site regions mention/include the existing MPAs (which will usually already exist longer than the MSP's)**
- 2.7. Does the MSP include explicit measures to ensure the protection of species in accordance with EU legislation and international commitments?
- 2.8. **Does the MSP allow for the future expansion of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) to meet the targets set out in the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030?**
- 2.9. **How are new MPAs included in MSP?***

Other questions

- 2.10. **Does the MSP indicate how the MSFD implementation process has informed the MSP?**
- 2.11. **Does the MSP provide a clear and transparent scientific rationale for the colocation (multi-use) of conservation areas and economic activities?**
- 2.12. Does the MSP provide for protected ecological corridors ensuring connectivity between conservation areas?
- 2.13. Are migratory routes for birds protected by the provisions of the MSP?
- 2.14. Does the MSP take explicit account of the life cycles of mobile marine species (birds, bats, fish and marine mammals)?
- 2.15. Does the MSP make specific provisions for the restoration of ecosystems?
- 2.16. Does the MSP include specific measures to mitigate the impacts of climate change on the marine ecosystem and allow for adaptation (e.g. migration of species)?
- 2.17. Does the MSP include specific measures to ensure marine ecosystems are not negatively impacted by marine traffic, fishing activity, tourism, aquaculture, marine renewables, coastal protection?
- 2.18. Does the MSP include specific measures to minimise the impact of noise and light pollution (e.g. from shipping and harbour activities)?
- 2.19. Is there consideration of how land-sea interactions can influence the focal biodiversity elements?
- 2.20. Are the MPAs/MSPs coherent with those of neighbouring countries? Can improvements be made?

Theme 2 Reserve questions

- 2.21. **How mature is the MSP process and how does that affect MSP effectiveness?***

Theme 3: The integration of social and economic aspects with MPAs

Theme 3 Core Questions:

- 3.1. Do you think that maritime uses are properly managed within MPA limits and through MSP with regards to MPA conservation objectives?
- 3.2. What are the main gaps or needs for management improvement?
 - 3.2.1. What are the most important management issues in your area: e.g. better understanding of multiple-pressures/impacts; improving co-existence between conservation and maritime activities; identifying trade-off between different stakeholder ambition, etc.?

Theme 3 Additional Questions:

Criteria, tools and trade off methods

- 3.3. **Are you aware of any criteria (e.g. ecosystem services) and tool useful to assess socio-economic aspects within MPAs?***
- 3.4. **Are you aware of any trade off methods useful to support decision making in MPAs prioritization?***

Consideration of human activities at sea

- 3.5. Do conservation areas explicitly exclude the following from taking place within or adjacent to their boundaries: commercial fishing; wind energy development; shipping; sand and gravel extraction; military use?
- 3.6. How is tourism taken into account during MPA planning and management? Can improvements be made?
- 3.7. How are fisheries taken into account during MPA planning and management? Can improvements be made?
- 3.8. How is aquaculture taken into account during MPA planning and management? Can improvements be made?
- 3.9. How are renewables taken into account during MPA planning and management? Can improvements be made?
- 3.10. How is marine traffic taken into account during MPA planning and management? Can improvements be made?
- 3.11. How is coastal protection taken into account during MPA planning and management? Can improvements be made?

Theme 3 Reserve Questions

- 3.12. - Does the licensing process of different economic sectors take into consideration MPAs? How is it done?*
- 3.13. - How are sectors monitoring their impact on MPAs in their surroundings?*
- 3.14. - What is the compensation of sectors for society and the environment? How is it measured/ managed?*

Theme 4: The (re)building of stakeholder confidence in the MPA/MSP implementation

Theme 4 Core Questions:

- 4.1. How are relevant actors involved in the MPA/MSP planning and management process?

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- 4.2. Does the current organisation of engagement efficiently build confidence and address properly the conservation and stakeholders' needs?
- 4.3. Are there any gaps in current practice of stakeholder engagement?
- 4.4. What could be the direction of improvement?

Stakeholder engagement tools

- 4.5. What type of tool would you recommend in order to facilitate stakeholder understanding of management issues and stakeholder engagement (e.g. graphical web interfaces, interactive maps, etc.)?*

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Annex 2: Template summary report desktop study and interviews with CoPs members

Background of interview participants

# participants	Type of stakeholder (Planning authority, MPA manager, Env. NGO, economic sector (which?), Researcher...)	Any further details

Interview format	# interviews
Face-to-face interviews	
(Online) calls	
Other (pls specify)	

Gender	# participants
Male	
Female	
Other	

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Country	# participants

Please find below the template for the integrated report for filling in the collected information (desktop analysis results part C combined with interview data). We require content for each theme, but subtopics can be removed where appropriate.

Questions with an * were not part of the desktop analysis but were requested as information for other WPs, and some are linked with questions we already included so those are combined with existing questions in the report template.

Thanks! WP5

Theme 1: Current status of MPA network

1/ Synthesis paragraph

2/ Core questions (each of them should be answered)

Reflections on current protection provided by network (1.1)

Any identified gaps in network coverage or network management (1.2)

Reflections on criteria and underpinning data for area designations (1.3)

3/ Detailed questions (Up to test site leader to select one or several to be answered)

Ecological and socio-economic criteria

Reflections on the criteria used for the identification of MPAs/OECMS and the underpinning scientific rationale (1.4*, 1.6)

Reflections on how social and economic criteria were addressed and/or could be addressed (1.5*, 1.7*)

Current MPA network and measures

Consideration of ecological connectivity in current MPA network (1.8*)

Consideration of MPA measures of climate change impacts on ecological features (1.9*)

Consideration of MPA measures of social and economic dimensions (1.10*)

Any features of interest (species, habitats, oceanographic, social, economic) currently lacking protection (1.11, 1.12*)

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Any gaps in current conservation objectives (1.13)

Effectiveness of management plans and management practices in achieving conservation objectives (1.14, 1.15)

Other findings/identified user needs related to this theme (including any answers to reserve questions)

Theme 2: The coherence between area designations and the (transboundary) MSP process as well as related governance such as MSFD

1/ Synthesis paragraph

2/ Core questions (each of them should be answered)

Coherence MPA and MSP processes (2.1, 2.2*)

Coherence MPA process with other environmental legislation such as MSFD or WFD (2.3)

MSP's role in avoidance of environmental impacts by maritime users (2.4)

3/ Detailed questions (Up to test site leader to select one or several to be answered)

Consideration of MPAs in MSP

MPA/MSP linkages and integration of new MPAs in MSP (2.5, 2.6, 2.9*)

Consideration by MSP of environmental EU legislation and international commitments, including the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 targets (2.7, 2.8)

Other subtopics

Indication of how MSFD has informed MSP (2.10)

Colocation of conservation areas and economic activities (2.11)

Connectivity, ecological corridors and migratory routes (2.12, 2.13)

Consideration of life cycles mobile marine species (birds, bats, fish and marine mammals) (2.14)

MSP initiatives related to ecosystem restoration (2.15)

MSP initiatives related to climate change mitigation and adaptation (2.16)

Any specific measures included in MSP to avoid environmental impacts of marine traffic, fishing activity, tourism, aquaculture, marine renewables, coastal protection on marine ecosystems (2.17)

Any specific measures included to minimise impact of noise and light pollution (e.g. from shipping and harbour activities) (2.18)

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Influence of land-sea interactions on focal biodiversity elements (2.19)

Coherence MPAs/MSPs of neighbouring countries (2.20)

Other findings/identified user needs related to this theme (including any answers to reserve questions)

Theme 3: The integration of social and economic aspects with MPAs

1/ Synthesis paragraph

2/ Core questions (each of them should be answered)

Management of maritime uses within MPA limits and through MSP in line with MPA conservation objectives, and any identified gaps (i.e. tourism, fisheries, aquaculture, renewables, marine traffic...) (3.1, 3.2, 3.2.1*)

3/ Detailed questions (Up to test site leader to select one or several to be answered)

Criteria, tools and trade off methods

Awareness interviewee of any criteria (e.g. ecosystem services) or tools to assess socio-economic impacts within MPAs (3.3*)

Awareness interviewee of any trade off methods used to prioritise MPAs (3.4*)

Consideration human activities at sea

Any exclusion of maritime uses in conservation areas (commercial fishing; wind energy development; shipping; sand and gravel extraction; military use) (3.5)

Consideration of maritime uses, such as coastal protection, during MPA planning and any identified gaps (3.6-3.11) Other findings/identified user needs related to this theme (including any answers to reserve questions)

Theme 4: The (re)building of stakeholder confidence in the MPA/MSP implementation

1/ Synthesis paragraph

2/ Core questions (each of them should be answered)

How are relevant actors involved in the MPA/MSP planning and management process? (4.1)

Does the current organisation of engagement efficiently build confidence and address properly the conservation and stakeholders' needs? (4.2)

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Any gaps in current practice of stakeholder engagement and any indication of potential direction of improvement (4.3, 4.4)

Stakeholder engagement tools

Any recommended tools to facilitate stakeholder engagement and their understanding of management issues (e.g. graphical web interfaces, interactive maps, etc.) (4.5*)

Other findings/identified user needs related to this theme (including any answers to reserve questions)

Any other themes identified during the data collection

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Annex 3: Guidelines for the 2nd interaction

1 - Aim the second interaction:

This document aims to provide common guidelines across the 6 test sites to carry out the 2nd interaction with CoP.

This interaction should address several needs for the project:

- Identification and prioritization of guiding questions, basis for the development of the ESE framework both from the environmental, social and economic point of view.
- Collect information to support T4.1 implementation
- Collect additional information to support T6.1 implementation

The practical format for this interaction should be chosen by test site leads according to local specificities, availability and demands of each CoPs. It could be a comprehensive workshop (online or in presence) addressing successively each of the 3 needs or a dedicated approach (meetings, interviews, questionnaires...) taken separately for each of those. However, it is very important to make a clear distinction between these 3 need to avoid confusion on the ESE approach which is the core approach of MSP4BIO.

Schedule: Ideally, the 2nd interaction should be done **by end-June 2023**

2- Elaboration and prioritization of guiding question

Presentation and exchanges during the GA in Ostende made it clear that the ESE framework (at least 1 and 2) is based on guiding questions coming from planners, decision makers or MPA managers. These questions are then specified by the identification of “practices” which could serve as basis for the development of improved criteria, indicators and tool that support an improved management.

It appears fundamental to start as early as possible the identification of these questions with regards to each test site specificities, relying on CoP expertise. This would enable project partner to have a view on the ongoing work directions and to evaluate whether they could be addressed given existing data, tools and methods.

Main principles for elaboration guiding questions

- ➔ The guiding questions should be classified according to the below template in order to keep the 4 key topics used for the first interaction with CoP members:
 - MPA network efficiency
 - Coherence between MPAs/OECMs and MSP
 - Social and economic aspects of the MPAs
 - Stakeholder confidence
- ➔ The guiding questions can be broken down into 3 levels of accuracy:
 - Level 1: Broad questions mainly referring to management issues (covering both ecological and social matters)

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- **Level 2:** Technical questions referring to different subjects by which management issues (level 1) could be tackled
 - **Level 3:** Detailed technical questions that can effectively guide the ESE implementation (selection of criteria, indicators and tools to be used for a given question) – equivalent to the “practices” term used in the ESE presentation
- ➔ The objective is to specify as much as possible guiding question from Level 1 to level 3. But it is not obliged to achieve this objective for each of the guiding questions with CoP. Some question may only be specified at Level 2 because it’s not relevant to go further in detail or due to a lack of knowledge of CoP members.
- ➔ Inversely, some very detailed question (level 3) could be raised out of the scope of a broader question (Level 2 or 1).
- ➔ Guiding question could cover different fields of analysis:
- Questions on ecosystem aspects (value assessment, approaches for protection...)
 - Question about social or economic aspects of conservation or MSP approaches
 - Policy-related questions
 - ...
- ➔ Information about end-users, scales, topics or MPS perspective could be collected, at least for level 1 question (maybe detailed for some level 2 or 3 questions if relevant), relying on the recommendations sent by WP3 and 4 leaders.

Template

Key topics	Guiding question			End-user	Scale	Topic	MSP Perspective Preparation / Planning/ Implementation/ Monitoring
	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3				
1. MPA Network							
2. MSP/MPA coordination							
3. Integration of social and economic							

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aspects within MPAs							
4. Stakeholder confidence in MPA/MSP implementation							

Recommendation on the format of the interaction

Type of meeting: Workshop with all the CoP members (online or in presence, as deemed appropriate)

Proposed method:

CoP 2nd interaction aims at:

- Making sure that all priority questions have been identified
- Specifying questions that could be tackled by one or several of the ESE.
- Filling in correspondent information (end-used, scale, topic...).

Preparation of material to support CoP discussion

Test site leads could formulate guiding questions based on the findings of the 1st interaction (reported in the T5.1) integrated report, and fill the table in with it. The level of detail of these questions from the 1st interaction will probably mainly fit with the level 1. But there could also be some more detailed questions.

The objective of this preliminary work is to be explicit on the link between the 1st and the 2nd CoP interaction and to provide initial thought to launch discussion.

In addition, if key questions that need to be addressed from the project point of view (CC, MPA locations toward an improved network, cumulative impacts...) were not mentioned during the first CoP interaction, WP leads could also propose additional questions (probably mainly level 1) to put in the table to orientate part of the reflection with CoPs.

The 2nd interaction meeting could be broken down into the following times

1. **Open discussion**
 - To specify as much as possible guiding questions already identified during the first interaction
 - to make as much questions as possible pop up
2. **Voting time** to prioritize the 4 most important **level 1** questions. Attention must be paid to the balance between preoccupations of different types of stakeholders to ensure that the diversity of stakeholders is represented in the prioritized questions.

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To do so, prioritization criteria should be set:

- Level of priority of the addressed challenge of issue for the territory.
- Level of impact of the potential solution in relation with the issue or challenge in the territory.
- Possibility for MSP4BIO to address the question (in terms of technical aspects or available knowledge and data)
- Balance between environmental, social and economic aspects

3. **Deepening analysis time** for the 4 questions with most votes:

- Identify existing criteria / data that can be used by ESE to answer
- Identify existing trade-off scenario (even at a smaller scale than the use case scale)

How to make use of the results after the 2nd interaction?

The 2nd interaction should fill the table in with prioritized guiding questions in relation with the context of each test sites. These questions should be as specified as possible by CoP members.

Then, results are provided to WP leads to:

- Evaluate technical possibility to address guiding question raised
- Potentially complete by adding some specified guiding questions thanks to project partner expertise (eg. By completing the list of practices (level 3) existing in relation with a technical question (level 2) raised by a CoP).

This feed-back could be communicated to CoP member for information and potential comments.

3 - Perception of social and economic aspects – T4.1

See T4.1 guidelines

4 - Collection of additional information on policy frameworks – T6.1

See T6.1 question

5 - APPENDIX

Appendix 1 – example of preliminary completed table

The below table is an example on how to fill in the template ahead of the 2nd CoP interaction – it should be tailored to each test site with specific questions arising from the 1st CoP interaction, to support exchanges of the 2nd interaction.

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In this example:

- **Blue cells** are questions coming from the WP3 and 4 recommendations
- **Red questions** are those taken from the French part of the Med test-site

Key topics	Guiding question			End-user	Scale	Topic	MSP Perspective Preparation / Planning/ Implementation/ Monitoring
	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3				
1. MPA Network	How to enlarge MPA network / strictly protected areas network? (e.g., in France the 5% target by 2027)	How can the newly created MPA be connected to an existing regional network of protected areas?	How can sink and source areas for target species be identified and integrated into the network?				
			How to assess and monitor connectivity between MPAs and non MPAs zones?				
		How to better address ecological functionalities in conservation objectives?					
		How to design cross-border coastal MPAs (e.g., protecting seagrass habitats)					
	How can the network cover mobile species?	How to evaluate area of interest for mobile species conservation at a basin scale?					
			How to design cross border coastal MPAs?				
	How to anticipate climate change effects in the network?	How can vulnerable species be protected against climatic stressors?					
			How to prioritize areas to be protected or existing network evolution according to CC?	How to anticipate the change in biotops?			
				How to identify the shelter areas?			

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	How to improve the monitoring of MPA efficiency?	What data needs to be collected and analysed to assess the effectiveness of the planned MPAs in meeting their conservation objectives?					
		What are the monitoring and evaluation requirements for the MPA?					
	How to protect MPAs from alien species invasion (preventive measure)?						
	How can a threatened habitat/species be restored?						
2. MSP/MPA coordination	What is the adapted scale for a given specie or habitat conservation?	Will the full legal protection cover the entire MPA area, or will there be different zones with different management objectives?					
		How could MSP or other global policies support connectivity between MPAs?	Are ecological corridor efficient?				
			Is there a need for global environmental target to ensure species movements between MPAs?				
		How to consider international conservation initiatives such as Pelagos sanctuary to bring coherence in national conservation or planning strategies?					
	How to evaluate effects (positive or negative) between MPAs and the vicinity?	What pressures from outside of the MPA could affect their conservation objectives?					
	How to evaluate the positive effects of conservation						

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		measures within MPAs for areas outside of the MPAs?					
	How to assess the blue economy at the basin level? (adapt the European taxonomies at a local level)						
3. Integration of social and economic aspects within MPAs	How to assess compatibility of maritime uses and MPAs conservation objectives, considering the local context?	How to get data on cumulative impacts of different activities or of an activity concentrated in one zone?					
		How to get proper sustainability criteria for maritime uses?					
		How to evaluate economic impacts of conservation measures?					
		How do the impacts of permitted activities in the MPA affect keystone species?					
		What are the uses monitoring and evaluation requirements for the MPA?					
		How to manage fish/shellfish stocks (e.g. issues with illegal catch)?					
4. Stakeholder confidence in MPA/MSZ implementation	How to develop clear monitoring criteria on protection within MPAs (and OECMs) and efficiency level (at the MPA scale and at the basin scale)?						

Appendix 2 – SMART approach to formulate guiding questions

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SMART questions

Specific: Be as precise as possible in formulating your question, don't hesitate to put a very specific question.

Measurable: Action-oriented: Suggest questions useful in MSP preparation/ monitoring/ revision/ implementation, as well as in MPA creation or management.

Relevant: Suggest questions that are at the core of the problem you are trying to solve.

Time-bound: if the problem you are trying to solve has time bound (e.g., by 2030, in the next 5 years, etc.), please indicate it.

Narrowing a broad question: it may be useful to start by formulating broad questions and then identify increasingly precise and smart sub-questions. Make the relationship between broad questions and smart sub-questions explicit.

Appendix 3 – Example of guiding question

EXAMPLE 1

- User: European Commission or sea basin commission officer for fishery
- Need: Sustainable management of fish population
- Question: How to make a fish population sustainable at sea basin level? [Broad question]
 - How can we effectively protect biodiversity and target species?
 - How can a network of interconnected marine protected areas be established?
 - How sink and source areas for the target species can be identified (research question)? [Narrow question]
- Topic: Ecological aspects
- Scale: Ecosystems, Local
- MSP Perspective: Preparation (stock taking); Planning (modeling sink and source areas); Implementation (Network of MPAs); Monitoring (target species)

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Annex 4: Material to support the 2nd interaction on socio-economic approach

4.1. Socio-economic approach: instructions for the 2nd CoP Interaction

Timing: 31st July, 2023

With some adaptations to adjust the needs of the MSP4Bio project, the following instructions are based on the method “*The Rapid Ecosystem Services Participatory Appraisal (RESPA)*” developed by Rey-Valette et al. (2017) which is a method of valuing ecosystem services based on perception surveys. The work of Sy et al. (2022) on the valuation of ecosystem services and social choice is also considered.

Preparation for the interaction: the first two steps should be done by the case study leader previous to your interaction with CoP members.

Step 1: Selection of geographical area

Two types of areas should be selected: one of the areas must be a current MPA of the case study and/or an area mentioned in the first CoP interaction (Gap analysis) that should be an area to be protected.

Suggestion:

i) selection of an area that most CoP members are more familiar with.

Step 2: Selection of potential ecosystem services for a given geographical area

Based on the CICES 5.1 Version, the researchers of UCA prepared a list with 27 Ecosystem Services (ES) related to coastal and marine areas ([Table Criteria vs ES, line 4](#)).

To facilitate your interaction with your CoP, pre-selected from this list the ES related to your geographical area.

Suggestion:

i) you can just delete the column of the ES that is not relevant to the geographical area analyzed.

Interaction with CoP members: After steps 1 and 2 be done, the case study leader can take the next steps with the CoP members.

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Step 3: Criteria Majority Judgment (MJ)

The principle of MJ is that the respondents explicitly express their opinions on the merit of every Criterion on a common ordinal scale of measurement, or language of grades, which were in our case defined as: “high priority”, “priority”, “neutral”, “low priority” and “not a priority”. CoP’s opinion should be based on the following conditions:

- I. it helps to define and/or modify coastal and marine areas for conservation purposes (natural or cultural heritage);
- II. it helps to manager uses and activities in a marine area (both for the MSP and for MPA zoning);
- III. It helps the management process, improving conservation and the planning of the uses and activities

A list with 20 socio-economic criteria ([Table Criteria vs ES, column A](#)) was developed by UCA researchers based on the list of criteria provided by the partners VLiz (environmental reference, e.g., MSFD) and UAc (MSP reference, e.g., UNESCO-IOC/European Commission (2021)).

- **Addition of new socio-economic and/or governance criterion: new criteria can be added, with their explanation/proposed indicators. Since the list of criteria presented here is based on a literature review made in Task 2.2 and Task 4.3, a brief explanation of why the criteria are being added is needed for justification purposes.**

Suggestion:

- i) if needed, explain the criteria in a way that your CoP member understands it better.

Step 4: Carrying out the perception survey on ecosystem services

Carry out a perception survey on ecosystem services with CoP Members. For every criterion (criterion ≠ “not a priority”), rank the ecosystem services associated with it by order of importance from the CoP member viewpoint.

Suggestion:

- i) if needed, explain the ES in a way that your CoP member understands it better.

Bibliography:

Sy, M.M., Figuières, C., Rey-Valette, H. et al. Valuation of ecosystem services and social choice: the impact of deliberation in the context of two different aggregation rules. Soc Choice Welf (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00355-022-01421-7>

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Rey-Valette, H., Mathé, S., & Salles, J. M. (2017). An assessment method of ecosystem services based on stakeholders perceptions: The Rapid Ecosystem Services Participatory Appraisal (RESPA). *Ecosystem Services*, 28, 311-319.

Annex 5: Guideline for trade-off interaction with CoP

Introduction

Welcome to this guide for carrying out the Trade-Off exercise as part of the MSP4BIO task T4.3 – Participatory development of integrated trade-off scenarios (ESE 4). To perform it, methodological guidelines were developed for participatory-based trade-off scenarios, to weigh the impacts of the multi-objective spatial and strategic management measures (i.e., uses impact on ecosystem services) in close interaction with T4.2 - Strategic and Spatial measures for blue economy sectors (ESE3). Using the set of tools provided by the toolkit in D3.5, the trade-off scenario methodology will also integrate a participatory mapping approach, thus providing an insight into the different perceived values of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) and their trade-offs (i.e., if spatial fishery restriction is to be imposed what is the social feedback?). Apart from looking for the best ways to mitigate conflicts among user groups, these guidelines will also focus on positive trade-offs or synergies between Ecosystem Services (ES), marine and coastal uses and human well-being.

Close interaction with the community of practice CoP is crucial since measures might change the local 'willingness to protect'. Participatory mapping will also be used to provide feedback to the Ecological Toolkit (D3.5), thus helping to structure prioritisation criteria by presenting maps of alternatives with high social acceptance. The climate change vulnerabilities criteria and maps (produced in T3.2) will be included in the trade-off scenarios to make them climate-proof and resilient in supporting biodiversity conservation and environmental protection or restoration of the ecosystem within a Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) framework and to identify internal and external social, economic, and ecological factors to achieve adequate protection and restoration.

The trade-off scenarios will be applied in the test sites (T5.3) and fed into an online scenario visualisation tool (T7.4) and the ESE framework (T4.4). The compilation of trade-offs in the case study sites will be provided in the frame of deliverable 4.3.

Marine Spatial Planning

Maritime spatial planning (MSP) is a process that involves the planning and management of human activities in marine areas to achieve ecological, economic, and social objectives that are usually specified through a political/public process. The MSP processes face the issue of finding solutions for multiple trade-offs between different human activities and conservation needs to guarantee the flow of ecosystem services that support human well-being while ensuring the healthy functioning of marine ecosystems.

Overall, MSPs must navigate these trade-offs to promote marine protection and resilience while also supporting sustainable economic development.

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The ultimate goal of addressing trade-offs in MSP is to achieve a more sustainable and integrated approach to managing marine resources and space, considering the long-term well-being of both societies and marine ecosystems.

Concepts

In the context of MSP, a trade-off refers to the compromise or exchange between different objectives, interests, or uses of marine resources and space. The decision-making process must weigh the potential benefits and costs associated with various uses or management options, considering ecological, social, and economical factors. Trade-offs in MSP require careful consideration and balancing of these different factors and interests.

Trade-offs can be addressed through stakeholder engagement, scientific analysis, and the use of decision-support tools (DST) to help identify optimal solutions that minimise negative impacts while maximising overall benefits. Trade-offs can arise in strict connection to specific goals, interests, and activities involved.

Different types of trade-offs might be found and organised as follows:

Trade-off between conservation and economic development objectives. MSP must balance the need to protect marine ecosystems while supporting economic activities such as fishing, shipping, and tourism. For example, designating MPAs can limit opportunities for fishing and tourism industries and thus the monetary revenue generated from those activities.

Trade-off between short-term and long-term benefits. MSP must balance the immediate benefits of certain activities with the long-term benefits of protecting marine ecosystems (e.g., allowing oil and gas exploration and drilling can provide short-term economic benefits but can also have long-term negative impacts on the environment and marine life).

Trade-off between exclusive uses and shared uses. When decisions about the allocation of marine space may involve trade-offs between exclusive use for a specific activity or multiple shared uses, on the same space or resource. Requires considering different stakeholder interests for that area and balancing between various uses, like fishing, marine protected areas, recreational zones, shipping lanes, etc.

Trade-off between specific stakeholder interests. Since different stakeholders may have different priorities and objectives. To advocate the interests of commercial fishermen, local communities, conservation organisations, researchers, maritime tour operators, and non-governmental organisations requires trade-offs to accommodate diverse perspectives.

Trade-offs between local and regional interests. While MSP can benefit local communities through economic development and job creation, it must also consider the

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impact of human activities on the global ocean ecosystem. For example, overfishing in one region can negatively impact fish populations in other regions.

These trade-offs are context-specific and depend on the particular circumstances of each MSP process. Identifying and managing these trade-offs effectively is important to achieve a balance and sustainable approach to marine resource management.

Ecosystem Services and Trade-off Analysis in MSP

The ES and trade-offs concepts are closely related within the field of environmental management.

Four main groups of ES can be identified based on the nature of the benefits humans received from healthy ecosystems, including tangible and intangible dimensions. These can be **provisioning services** such as food, fresh water, biochemicals, and genetic resources; **regulating services** such as climate regulation, disease regulation, water regulation, water purification, and pollination; **cultural services** such as recreation and tourism, as well as spiritual and religious, aesthetic, inspirational, and educational benefits; and **supporting services** such as soil formation, nutrient cycling, and primary production.

Trade-offs occur when pursuing one objective or maximizing the use of a particular ecosystem service comes at the expense of other services or priorities. Trade-offs arise when managing ecosystem services and deciding how to allocate multiple resources. For example, converting a natural coastal ecosystem into a tourism enterprise may lead to habitats and species loss and reduced water filtration capacity, affecting other services such as coastal protection and water quality.

The relation between trade-offs and ecosystem services regularly requires **assigning values to these services**. The valuation can be done by economic measures (e.g., monetary valuation) as well as non-monetary approaches that consider social and cultural values (e.g., importance/ relevance for the community). These can help quantify the benefits and costs associated with different services, comparing and assessing trade-offs easier.

Trade-offs in ecosystem services are central to decision-making processes. In these processes, stakeholders and decision-makers evaluate the potential impacts of different management options and consider the trade-offs involved. Recognising and managing trade-offs is essential for integrated ecosystem management and sustainable development. Decision-makers can aim for a more holistic and balanced approach to resource management, striving to optimise the overall benefits while minimising negative impacts.

These integrated approaches help identify win-win solutions or strategies for synergies among ecosystem services. To achieve more sustainable and equitable outcomes, trade-offs can be managed by considering the interdependencies among ecosystem services.

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Understanding the relationship between ecosystem services and trade-offs can help the decision-making process, ensuring that trade-offs are carefully evaluated, and sustainable management strategies are pursued.

Methodology to map Ecosystem services

What exists – This step is supported/performed by UAc Team

The first step is to explore existing geographical information supporting ecosystem services in each study case. With the results of T4.1, the three most important ecosystem services for each study site are able to be highlight. To select these three most important ES, the ranking of each ecosystem service and the percentage of answers possible must be checked. The higher the percentage, the more reliable the ranking of ecosystem services.

Then, explore each criterion related to the three most important ecosystem services in order to know which criteria are useful to map in each pilot's sites. The task 4.1 linked the various criteria to each ecosystem services.

Finally, to map each criterion, check all the useful data on T 2.2.

Methods to map ES

In order to map each criterion, two methods were chosen: criteria overlay and hotspot of information/Bio layers. They are explained in the following points.

This involves mapping the biophysical characteristics of ecosystems that contribute to the provision of ecosystem services.

Criteria overlay (Azores proposal)

The first method identified for mapping ecosystem services is to overlay each criteria related to the ecosystem services. The Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis is a method to structure and formalize decision-making process, but it would require expert judgement.

The positive aspects of this method are that it is robust but requires time and human resources.

Hotspot of information

To create this type of map, an overlay all information about the ecosystem component layers must be produced. This method will aggregate the binary assessment of the contribution of the ecosystem services for each ecosystem component. This method will therefore highlight the areas with the most ecosystem services support.

This method has the advantage of being simple to use and requires limited human and time resources. However, the disadvantage is that it is not as robust. Indeed, it only considers the presence or the absence of information about the ecosystem to produce

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the map. Moreover, each component of the map is considered equal. This implies a reduction in the accuracy of the information we want to represent (HELCOM, 2023).

Participatory Mapping

There are various tools available for participatory mapping. Burnett (2023) edited a book titled "Evaluating Participatory Mapping Software," which lists tools and their respective strategies for efficient data collection suited to different needs. The compiled material, along with other tools, is presented in Table 1 at the end of this document. However, it is important to note that the solutions presented in the table should not limit the choice of methodologies for each case study. Case site leaders are free to choose the most appropriate methodology for their project according to the general outline and process steps.

For those partners who prefer using SeaSketch software (SeaSketch, 2023), training is arranged with project developer Will McClintock. The training will take place after the next GA Meeting on the 8th and 9th of November 2023 in a hybrid format. We recommend that case study leaders have the GIS information for their area beforehand in preparation for the training.

Step-by-step methodology

Remember that this methodology will be used along with:

Annex 01 – Portfolio of arguments to support trade-offs.

Annex 02 – Example of Survey for Graciosa Island ([in SeaSketch](#)).

Annex 03 – Example of Graciosa Scenarios.

Annex 04 – PowerPoint – What is a trade-off.

Annex 05 – Layout/guidelines for reporting.

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Before III CoP interaction (planned for November/December)

- A.1. Based on the geographic information (identified in Task 5.1 and Task 2.1), make a folder exclusive of your case study with the download of all GIS and include it in a working folder (can be [here](#)).
- A.2. Make a list of criteria/ecosystem services listed and ordered by priority (identified in Tasks 4.1) for your case site (UAc Team is supporting this step).
- A.3. Identify a natural value to be protected. (e.g. Dark Coral) and Define Conservation Goal (e.g. protect 20% of Dark Coral).
- A.4. Choose a tool to develop the work (See table 01 for suggestions). For those who choose SeaSketch, face-to-face/online training will be conducted on the 8th and 9th in Split, after the GA Meeting with the tool developer Will McClintock. **If you bring all your materials organised, you can directly develop the survey tool there.**

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- A.4.1. Include the spatial data in the tool to be used (you should have this done before the SeaSketch training if you want to use this tool i.e before 7/8 November);
- A.4.2. Create a "participatory mapping survey" for your case study that can bring CoP to answer the guiding questions (Task 5.3) and consider the prioritised criteria (A.2). Remember to include open questions for collaborative mapping on important areas for specific activities, areas of conflict, and areas of synergy;

The questionnaire will be in three Parts I, II and III; The Graciosa survey can be used to inspire your questionnaire ([Graciosa example](#));

- A.4.2.1. "Participatory Mapping Survey" Part I – Data Collection and perception;

For those using SeasSketch, you can use the training to start designing the survey; the goal is to collect spatial information about uses (existing and potential), conflict areas and possible valuation of areas for trade-offs. Those using other participatory mapping tools (PPMT) will have to adapt to their tool.

Examples of questions:

- Map known/ licensed existing uses in your area.
- How is your use in the area?
- Map areas of conflict.
- Areas with potential for expansion or relocation of your activity?
- What are the priority areas for conservation?

- A.4.2.2. "Participatory Mapping Survey" Part II – Showcase the data analysis and validate; Draw scenario examples based on the uses, conflicts and services criteria (which you can learn to develop during the workshop with Will in Split); these are to be discussed on part 2 of the interaction and agreed upon the consensual solution. (See 2.1.7).

Examples of possible analysis will be delivered by the SeaSketch team.

- A.4.2.3. "Climate Change Perception Analysis" Part III – Explain the Climate Change (CC) projections/ scenarios for your area. Do a perception of impacts analysis with the participatory mapping tool.

Examples of questions:

- How likely it will change with CC

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- How does CC affect the use of Ecosystems services?
- How does CC will affect your use?
- What would be the Climate Change impact (-5 = negative impact; 5 = positive impact)?
- How can we adapt to Climate Change in the area?

At least 3 hours of a face-to-face workshop is recommended (to be adjusted by each case study leader).

During the meeting

A.5. Making the participatory trade-offs.

A.5.1. Explain what trade-offs are (2/3 slides provided by UAc Team in the [annexe 04](#));

A.5.2. Based on what was identified in 5.1 (guiding questions), present issues to be discussed/ addressed at the meeting (optional);

A.5.3. Remind the criteria/ ecosystem services ranked during II CoP interaction (Task 4.1);

A.5.4. Present the ecological values of your case study (WP3 results to be confirmed VME or any natural value or specie);

a. For the case sites where it has been decided to create a new MPA in the last CoP interaction: 1. point it out 2. **draw the new protected area** 3. Identify Ecosystem Services in the Area

b. or other important feature to protect and 1. what extent of protection you are aiming (20%, 30%...); **Establish a clear objective for the discussion and 2. draw it on the map**; 3. Identify Ecosystem Services in the Area.

A.5.5. Pass out the questionnaire (A.4.2.1 – Part I) for CoP members to interact on (remember to map important areas for specific activities, areas of conflict, and areas of synergy); The intention is to pass part I in a morning event and Part B in the afternoon;

A.5.6. Develop Scenarios mapping (A.4.2.2 – Part II);

A.5.7. Develop Climate Change analysis (A.4.2.3 – Part III)

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A.5.8. Make the analysis together with the CoP members. Create possible scenarios based on the priority criteria/ rank of Ecosystem Services Importance of your case study (example of Graciosa in [annexe 03](#));

A.5.9. "Vote" to decide which agreements may be relevant for the region according to the specific needs of your case study. Structure prioritisation criteria by presenting maps of alternatives with high social acceptance. Use the "Arguments Portfolio" in annex **XX** to negotiate your solution;

A.6. Write down the main points of discussion (as per the template that will be provided).

A.7. Registration of the meeting (photo/print screen/recording).

A.8. Download the maps into your GIS folder (allocated in WP4 – 4.3 in [SharePoint](#)).

After the meeting

A.9. Deliver activity reports to UAc by 31/12.

A.10. Send feedback to CoP members (D4.3) by March/2024, after the Deliverable 4.3 approval (optional).

Complementary literature

Austen, M., Andersen, P., Armstrong, C., Döring, R., Hynes, S., Levrel, H., ... & Coopman, J. (2019). Valuing Marine Ecosystems-Taking into account the value of ecosystem benefits in the Blue Economy (No. vy3kp). Center for Open Science.

Burnett, C. M. (2023). *Evaluating Participatory Mapping Software* (C. M. Burnett (ed.)). Springer Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-19594-5>.

Daily, G. C., & Matson, P. A. (2008). Ecosystem services: From theory to implementation. *Proceedings of the national academy of sciences*, 105(28), 9455-9456.

HELCOM. 2023. 'Thematic Assessment of Economic and Social Analyses 2016-2021'. HOLAS III. <https://helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/HELCOM-Thematic-assessment-of-economic-and-social-analyses-2016-2021.pdf>.

Ivarsson, M., Magnussen, K., Heiskanen, A. S., Navrud, S., & Viitasalo, M. (2017). Ecosystem services in MSP: Ecosystem services approach as a common Nordic understanding for MSP. Nordic Council of Ministers.

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- Lester, S. E., Costello, C., Halpern, B. S., Gaines, S. D., White, C., & Barth, J. A. (2013). Evaluating tradeoffs among ecosystem services to inform marine spatial planning. *Marine Policy*, 38, 80–89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2012.05.022>.
- Lester, S. E., Stevens, J. M., Gentry, R. R., Kappel, C. V., Bell, T. W., Costello, C. J., Gaines, S. D., Kiefer, D. A., Maue, C. C., Rensel, J. E., Simons, R. D., Washburn, L., & White, C. (2018). Marine spatial planning makes room for offshore aquaculture in crowded coastal waters. *Nature Communications*, 9(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-03249-1>.
- SeaSketch projects (2023). McClintock labs. Marine Science Center. University of California Santa Barbara <https://www.seasketch.org/projects/>
- White, C., Halpern, B. S., & Kappel, C. V. (2012). Ecosystem service tradeoff analysis reveals the value of marine spatial planning for multiple ocean uses. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 109(12), 4696–4701. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1114215109>.

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Annex 6: Guidelines for the 4th interaction with CoPs

Aim of the fourth interaction

1. Showcase [ESE framework](#) developments to CoP Members and collect feedbacks according to evaluation questionnaire provided by ESE developers.
2. Show perspectives according to priorities / guiding questions already expressed by CoP members and prioritize site-specific solutions to be developed until month 28 (we should have deliverable 5.3 submitted on the 32 month).

The format of this fourth interaction is free and could be adapted to each local context: in presence, remotely, individual interviews...

ESE developments presentation

- Initial tool-based step by step ESE ready for testing: [ESE framework](#)
- CoP Members feedbacks according to ESE developer's evaluation questionnaire (<https://forms.gle/wuHYZZXJhQHjilFo8>)

Perspectives for site specific solutions to be developed

Need to rely on Task 4.3 Trade-offs results and T5.2 outputs => Sum up of guiding question and pre-identification of ESE components to be implemented.

To prepare next CoP interaction:

- D5.2 with regards to ESE => Pre-identification of ESE modules to be mobilized
- Go through D2.1 + local knowledge to identify data that could be used to implement chosen ESE modules

Reporting template for the 4th CoP interaction

Attendance

- ⇒ Who took part of this 4th interaction? What are their management duties, their field of expertise?

ESE introduction

- ⇒ Was ESE conceptual model and toolkit well understood? What are the remaining clarification needs?
- ⇒ What kind of needs could be suited thanks to ESE implementation?
- ⇒ What are the modules pointed out as useful to do so, from CoP members' point of view?
- ⇒ Were difficulties foreseen in the upcoming ESE implementation? What are the main reasons? Is there any suggestion to overcome these difficulties?

Toward ESE implementation

- ⇒ Were proposed guiding question agreed by CoP members? Is there any additional question/need?
- ⇒ What are the ESE modules identified to address these questions?

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- ⇒ Which DSTs could be tested and demonstrated to specific test site?
- ⇒ Are existing data and knowledge thought as sufficient to implement selected ESE modules?
- ⇒ What are the alternative solutions considered?

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Annex 7: Communities of practice feedback 2025

COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICE FEEDBACK 2025

- Positive feedback
- Feedback to learn from
- Suggestions

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COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICE FEEDBACK 2025

- Positive feedback
- Feedback to learn from
- Suggestions

USEFULNESS OF KEY RESULTS

Implementation of MSP4BIO tools

4

All MSP4BIO tools have been implemented in CoPs with the *Portfolio of ecological criteria, policy coherence solutions, test site solutions, the Ecological Toolkit* and *Nature inclusive design of blue economy sectors* being used the most across test sites. Trade off approaches and SeaSketch were very much appreciated across all test sites and CoPs show interest to use these tools in the future.

Usefulness of tools in respective CoP context

5

Ranking of tools:

- 4.5/5 ESE Framework
- 4.5/5 Nature inclusive design of BE sectors
- 4.5/5 Policy Coherence Solutions
- 4.3/5 Test Site Solutions
- 4/5 Ecological Toolkit (ESE1)
- 4/5 Climate-Smart MPAs Guidance
- 3.6/5 Portfolio of improved Ecological Criteria
- 3.5/5 Socio-economic Criteria for MPAs (ESE2)

Sharing of MSP4BIO tools beyond CoPs

6

Two CoPs shared MSP4BIO tools with relevant partners from their network. One CoP is still planning on sharing MSP4BIO tools, two reported they did not share tools.

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COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICE FEEDBACK 2025

- Positive feedback
- Feedback to learn from
- Suggestions

CONTRIBUTION TO POLICY OR PRACTICE

Influence of MSP4BIO on policy processes

7

CoPs shared that MSP4BIO already has or will influence the following processes in the future:

- National or regional MSP plans**
- Marine protection or restoration strategies**
- Cross-border cooperation initiatives**
- Institutional capacity-building**
- Policy development and governance**

One CoP reported that none of the above have been influenced until now.

Potential for Uptake of the MSP4BIO tools

8

1. The Azores test site has already taken up site-specific solutions by agreeing on an MPA expansion for the area.
2. In the Baltic Sea, authorities are already building on MSP4Bio ESE1 and policy solutions.
3. CoPs expressed interest to implement trade-off approaches and SeaSketch in the future.

1. A transboundary synthesis on marine mammals and VME-related issues could support the launch of a CoP in the Pelagos Sanctuary.
2. Foster public-public, public-private, and public-community partnerships to enable effective implementation.
3. Tools could stimulate specific conservation actions through improved coordination and stakeholder engagement.
4. Apply MSP4BIO tools in planning and integrating diverse activities in multifunctional marine zones.

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COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICE FEEDBACK 2025

- Positive feedback
- Feedback to learn from
- Suggestions

VALIDATION AND IMPROVEMENT

Reflection of MSP/MPA community needs

9

Yes, the results correspond to the main needs and challenges filling knowledge gaps of the community. MSP4BIO helps facilitating policy integration at the local level.

The applicability should be further examined in test sites to validate the above mentioned statements.

Integration in local or national MSP/MPA processes

10

A solid foundation and enhanced communication now enable smoother integration into key local and national processes. MSP4BIO results could support in the implementation of strict protection, MPA management and knowledge of VME in the local area of the CoP.

The underlying structure of administrations and the fear of change could derail the adoption of new policies.

Areas for improvement

11

- Develop new environmental indicators (e.g. functionality, climate sensitivity).
- Strengthen interdisciplinary skills for territorial management.
- Share and present results proactively to the public.
- Hold open discussions with stakeholders to align results with policy.

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COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICE FEEDBACK 2025

- Positive feedback
- Feedback to learn from
- Suggestions

ENGAGEMENT AND FUTURE COLLABORATION

Satisfaction with engagement opportunities

12

4.5/5

The workshop organised in the CoP provided opportunity to build a common understanding of the management processes on both sides of the border (science/policy).

Areas of interest for future activities or projects

13

- Supporting cross-border cooperation and regulatory alignment.
- Participating in workshops and idea-sharing.
- Contributing as partners or stakeholders with relevant expertise.
- Joining a follow-up community of practice through webinars and meetings.

Likelihood of CoPs participating in future activities

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